

ORIGINAL PAPER

Bringing back cattle grazing to abandoned farmlands. A lesson from silvopastoral ecological intensification in the landscape of the Carpathian foothills, SE Poland

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ABSTRACT

Development of the modern, highly specialised and economically efficient, forestry in the 1700s has substantially changed the structural characteristics and dynamics of European woodlands. In particular, the ban on forest grazing that had been almost universally adopted throughout all Central Europe, unleashed the processes of development of shade-tolerant undergrowth, leading to the loss of semi-open woods and to functional, ecological, isolation of forests from the wider landscape context. In a separate development, due the recent socio-economic changes, scores of farmland have been abandoned, turning variegated countryside to feral landscapes, increasingly covered by woody vegetation. Although such changes are in line with recommendations focused on the climate issues, we believe that the ‘ecological intensification’ of the abandoned landscapes may provide more benefits than their permanent abandonment. In order to verify that intuition, we studied ecological features and silvopastoral benefits of a landscape unit in the Carpathian foothills of SE Poland, which, during the last twelve years has been grazed by cattle, let in after the former ten years since the agricultural abandonment. We provide the information on the landscape’s mosaic structure with regard to the habitats use by cat-

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Received: 11 December 2023; Revised: 21 February 2024; Accepted: 23 February 2024; Available online: 10 May 2024

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tle. In addition, we investigated the animals' reaction to the exposure of the local arboreal forage, of which the chemistry and nutritional values have been compared to those of the herbaceous one. As shown by the study, cattle can be used as a factor successfully preventing succession and sustaining the balance between wooded and non-wooded habitats. We revealed that the wood-pasture's tree hay was very attractive to cattle, compensating deficits of the herbaceous fodder. Our study proved that the grazing herd of robust cattle breeds can turn a feral, post-agricultural land into a working wood-pasture, consisting of interconnected open grasslands and various facets of woodland, some of them missing in contemporary high forests. Such landscapes can provide multiple ecosystem services, scarce or absent in abandoned, overgrown farmlands. We advocate, therefore, for the transition management of abandoned farmlands towards the integrated silvopastoral land use, contributing to the land's economic value and landscape's ecosystem services, and the restoration of woodland's characteristics, disappeared in contemporary forests.

KEY WORDS

agroforestry, Carpathian foothills, grazing ecology, land abandonment, semi-open woods, tree hay, wood-pasture

Introduction

Modern forestry, as developed by Saxon school in the 1700s, was based on the rule of 'sustainable yield' (von Carlowitz, 1713). Focused on efficiency of timber growth, it implies eliminating or at least minimizing impacts of factors, which could reduce the volume or quality of the expected crop. Among other undesirable factors, livestock grazing has commonly been indicated as the 'enemy no. one' of a forest (Holzl, 2010). Ban on forest grazing has become almost universally adopted throughout the countries following the German way of forestry, including Poland. It led to substantial structural and compositional changes of forests, which, in particular, have lost their semi-open species-rich ecotonal zone, a dynamic forest-farmland interface, where grazing was a major driver fostering migration of species. As shown by Bobiec *et al.* (2019) and Wolański *et al.* (2021), elimination of forest grazing enabled development of a dense shrub buffer, sealing off the woodland's edge and leading to their ecological segregation from the non-forest neighbourhood.

Contemporary dense, tall temperate forests, whether managed for economic use or preserved in protected areas, substantially differ from historic Europe's woodlands, subjected to multiple uses, involving coppicing, grazing, racking litter, 'tree hay' making (Rackham, 2006). Such a 'woodmanship' implied a very different disturbance regime to the one entailed by modern forestry and its silviculture focused on the production of high-quality, long, slender and knot-free logs. For obvious reasons, traditional peasant 'plunder cutting' combined with coppicing, tree shredding, grazing, and collecting litter (resulting in nutrients depletion), would compromise the goal of the science-based silviculture. However, traditional historic use of woodland was beneficial and in numerous instances even indispensable for development of a variety of ecological and aesthetic traits and qualities that we consider and appreciate as important, valuable, and beautiful. In temperate Central Europe, the richest in vascular plant species semi-open oak woods, *Quercetalia pubescenti-petraeae* Klika 1933 corr. Moravec in Beg. et Theurill 1984 (the EU priority habitat 91I0), have almost completely been turned to much poorer closed-canopy hornbeam-dominated forest habitats *Tilio cordatae-Carpinetum betuli* Tracz. 1962, due to grazing abandonment (Faliński, 1986; Sokółowski, 1993; Jaroszewicz *et al.*, 2020). With the common-sense philosophy (well expressed by 'take the best leave the rest', the well-known saying among forest owners in New York State)

underpinning the traditional, peasant model of wood cutting, ancient woodlands abounded in gnarled, knotty, cavity and crevice-rich ‘veteran’ trees. Their irreplaceable value of biodiversity hotspots has been widely recognised (Gough *et al.*, 2014; Horak *et al.*, 2014; Sebek *et al.*, 2016). Last but not least, semi-open woods or savanna-like habitats offer a very special aesthetic quality, absent in contemporary close-canopy forests, whether commercially used or preserved in protected areas. As suggested by the ‘savannah theory’ of evolutionary psychology, people are attracted to the ambience of semi-open, light woods, offering a sense of harmony, quiet, and security (Appleton, 1975; Orians and Heerwagen, 1992; Sommer, 1997).

Considering that the Potential Natural Vegetation (*sensu* R. Tüxen – Tüxen, 1956), Central Europe (CE) is almost entirely dominated by various types of deciduous and mixed forest communities (Matuszkiewicz, 2008a, b). The end point of the ecological succession on abandoned landscapes are dense forests. The evidence of this is particularly obvious in the eastern part of the Carpathian region, shared by Poland, Ukraine, and Slovakia, where, as a consequence of World War II (WWII), many communities were displaced and their villages deserted. Seventy years later, scores of former pastures, arable land, fruit orchards, and semi-open grazed woods have turned to high forests – either due to ecological succession or to the afforestation policy (Affek *et al.*, 2021; Zarzycki *et al.*, 2022). With its Forest strategy for 2030, the European Union appreciates such a course and advises its furthering to meet greenhouse gas emission reduction targets (of at least 55% by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050) as well as to improve the state of biodiversity (EC 2021). However, a growing number of studies reveals the adverse effects of abandonment and succession of woody vegetation on various aspects of biodiversity (Matuszkiewicz, 2008b; Affek *et al.*, 2021; Zarzycki *et al.*, 2022). According to Lomba *et al.* (2019), High Nature Value farmlands (HNVfs), supporting a wide range of ecosystem services, including the conservation of biodiversity, provide a more socio-economically viable option than letting a land to follow spontaneous succession. The low-intensity HNV farming systems, depending on socio-economic embedment in local landscapes’ ecologies, are essential for the long-lasting resilience of bio-cultural systems (MacDonald *et al.*, 2000; Navarro and Pereira, 2012). Social and economic decoupling from immediate ecological context, in particular landscapes (Brambilla *et al.*, 2017), leads to progressing human alienation (Biró *et al.*, 2020), generational amnesia (Lomba *et al.*, 2019), irreversible erosion of traditional ecological knowledge (Liu *et al.*, 2007), and threatens food security (Kirwan, 2011; Rotherham, 2013).

With the present pioneering research, we would like to provide multiple premises for an alternative, proactive approach to abandoned rural landscapes being commonplace in South-Eastern (SE) Poland as well as in most of the Carpathian region. We demonstrate the landscape structure as developed in response to cattle grazing introduced ten years after agricultural abandonment and spontaneous succession, involving development of young pioneering tree groves, wild fruit shrubs and brambles, and numerous oak saplings. After twelve years of grazing the landscape turned to structurally variegated wood-pasture. We investigated the spatial pattern of its use by free-range grazing livestock, with regard to its preferences towards particular types of habitat. Specifically, we were interested in the intensity of the cattle presence in the patches of forest habitats – a situation that has been legally prohibited for fifty years in Poland. The study also involved experimental cattle feeding with tree leafage, subject to chemical and nutritious comparison to herbaceous fodder. Considering the development of the studied landscape unit, we reflected on the changing structure of ecosystem services resulting from two alternative scenarios of an abandoned farmland: spontaneous rewilding vs. transformation to economically used wood-pasture.

Materials and method

STUDY AREA. The study was performed in the Carpathian foothills (SE Poland), ca. 10 km south-east from the centre of Rzeszów (Fig. 1A). Due to the post-communist economic transformation of the 1990s and early 2000s thousands of multiple-use (semi-)subsistence family farms declined, scores of ploughfields, meadows, and pastures, including those in the study area, were abandoned (Lomba *et al.*, 2019). Such was the fate of the small village Borówki, Chmielnik commune, where in early 2000s, the local cooperative acquired ca. 30 ha of a hilly farmland consisting of abandoned ploughfields, patches of woods as well as grassland with scattered wild cherry trees *Cerasus avium* (L.) Moench, common oaks *Quercus robur* L., sycamore maples *Acer pseudoplatanus* L., and black alders *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. By then, parts of fallow fields were colonised by birch *Betula pendula* Roth and alder saplings, accompanied by young oaks, sycamore maples, and hornbeams *Carpinus betulus* L. The study focused on the half of that area (16.3 ha) fenced, and subjected to grazing by the Galloway cattle, which was first let to free roam in 2008 (Fig. 1). The herd, substantially exceeding the pasture grazing capacity (80 adult individuals and ca. 40 calves) receives supplementary fodder – locally acquired hay and haylage. Being a part of a circular farming system, animals are also fed with vegetable left-overs from the local fruit-vegetable operation. The herd spends most of the daytime of the grazing season (late April to early November) in the wood-pasture, gathering under large shelter after the dark or during major weather breakdowns.

Fig. 1.

The studied landscape's location and physiognomy

A – study area location, B – four zones of tree stem density (number of stems per 2000 m² and white rectangular area in the north indicating the fenced farmstead enclave, C – LiDAR terrain model (source: MassGIS Data: Lidar DEM and Shaded Relief – <https://www.mass.gov/info-details/massgis-data-lidar-dem-and-shaded-relief>), D – treescape)

VEGETATION ANALYSIS OF THE CATTLE-GRAZED WOOD-PASTURE. We used Yuneec H520 with E90 camera (23 mm F/2.8) to acquire the high-resolution ortophotomap (20 MP, *ca.* 1.2 cm/px), in the optimal autumn trees phenological stage (late October, 2020). The ortophotomap and the terrain model was used for the delineation of the apparent vegetation categories: open, treeless grassland (OGR), pioneering groves dominated by birch or alder (PIG), semi-open woods (SOW), close-canopy woods (CCW), and riparian woods (RIW) (Fig. 2)

In early July 2021, in 32 arbitrarily chosen locations, representing typical aspects of each vegetation category, 10×10 m phytosociological relevés were made. Using six-interval relevés' coverage ('+' <1%, '1' 1-5%, '2' 6-25%, '3' 26-50%, '4' 51-75%, '5' >75%), abundances of vascular plant species were assessed as a basis for the zones' phytosociological classification (Braun-Blanquet and Pavillard, 1925). For the nomenclature of phytosociological syntaxonomic categories and for the species' phytosociological affiliation we referred to Matuszkiewicz (2008a); species nomenclature after Mirek *et al.* (2002). In detailed phytosociological analyses, neither tree nor shrub seedlings were considered, due to their small diagnostic value. In addition, the ortophotomap was used to digitise the stems of the stand's canopy layer (Fig. 1, 3). With the 'Kernel Density

Fig. 2.

Five distinguished types of the Borówki wood pasture

A, C – semi-open woods (SOW), first dominated by wild cherry and silver birch and the second one by hornbeam and oak; B – close-canopy wood (CCW), mostly used by cattle for rest; D, E – open grassland (OGR) neighbouring with pioneering groves (PIG), dominated by silver birch, developed on former plough fields; F – riparian wood (RIW)

Fig. 3.

Wood-pasture as a variegated landscape

A – the distribution of stems of the most frequent tree species; Qr – *Quercus robur*; Ca – *Cerasius acium*, Ap – *Acer pseudoplatanus*, Cb – *Carpinus betulus*, Bp – *Betula pendula*, Ag – *Alnus glutinosa*, Fs – *Fagus sylvatica* L. B – the major habitat categories; nine red dots – places of the leafage experimental exposure; for habitat types see Figure 2

Estimation' QGIS plug-in (radius 25 m, ca. 2000 m²), the point values of stand density were estimated. Based on the resulting 'heat map', we generated isolines (QGIS, contour cutting =5; Fig. 1) and tree stem density zones, corresponding with five distinguished vegetation categories (Fig. 3).

In order to assess the possible effect of livestock grazing on plant movement across the landscape mosaic, we categorised the herbaceous species affiliations to phytosociological classes as either grassland species, or forest species, or ruderal species, or species belonging to mantle and fringe shrubland vegetation. Compositional affinities and similarities between forest and non-forest neighbouring habitats were used as a proxy measure of possible zoochoric pathways of plants across the landscape (the 2-sample test for equality of proportions with continuity correction).

SPATIAL PATTERN AND DYNAMICS OF THE WOOD-PASTURE USE BY CATTLE

Cattle itineraries on the wood-pasture. Involving four, randomly selected adult herd's cows, the round-the-clock movement pattern of animals through the mosaic of five habitat categories was explored. They were tagged with COBAN TK108B 10000 mAh track-loggers placed in canvas bags, fixed to the neck collars on June 24th 2020 and the cows' position data logging, with 10-s interval, started on midnight 25/26 June and lasted till midnight 28/29 June 2020 of four cows. Based on the spatial density of the impulses (i.e., cows' geo-impulses per 100 m²) recorded by the track-loggers, we estimated the relative exploitation intensities of particular habitat types as well as inter-habitats' 10-m-wide transition zones (ecotones). The ecotones were determined in QGIS as the borderlines' each side 5-m-wide buffers. Analysing the movements between neighbouring habitats, we assessed the spatial-dynamic pattern of cattle's use of the variegated landscape.

Temporary cattle groupings and livestock temporal impact on the wood-pasture. From July 7th to 9th, the herd was discreetly observed from 7 AM to 5 PM, and the temporary cattle groupings (TCGs,

including bulls, cows, and heifers, excluding calves), occupying distinct wood-pasture areas (Fig. 4: right) were mapped with the use of Field-Map (IFER) system coupled with Trupulse 360B (Laser Technology) range-finder and their durations were assessed. On the basis of the multiple-point groupings, ‘standard deviational ellipses’ (Wang *et al.*, 2015) were calculated with the QGIS plugin – a synthetic spatial representation of TCGs (Fig. 4). Thereafter, we calculated the livestock temporal impact on herbaceous forages (LTI) in the wood-pasture as:

$$LTI = n_i \cdot t_i \cdot ASDE(i)^{-1}$$

where:

n_i – number of animals in the i -th TCG,

t_i – the i -th TCG duration,

$ASDE(i)$ – the area of the i -th standard deviational (SD) ellipse.

Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess the differences in the size of TCGs (*i.e.*, the number of animals in TCGs and the SD ellipses’ areas) between the three observation days, while cattle preferences for the five habitats were assessed by tests of single proportion and multiple proportions (Marascuilo, 1966)

Cattle feeding pattern on arboreal forages. To understand how cattle feed on fresh arboreal forages, we selected fourteen trees as representative sources in the wood-pasture: birch (2 trees), alder (1), oak (3), wild cherry (3), sycamore maple (3), and hornbeam (2). Nine of them were pollarded on July 2nd and five on July 7th. While the branches of each of the first nine trees were cut-off and placed at 3-5 m away from each tree as multiple-species stacks (Fig. 5), the whole crowns of the latter five trees were felled, and left close to each tree without cutting the branches (Fig. 5). The stacks/crowns were represented by their perimeter polygons extended to the 2-m-wide buffers, an average length of a cow. To collect data on attractiveness of the arboreal forages to cattle, immediately after having established the forage posts, Acorn Ecotone phototraps were installed on neighbouring trees to film the attracted animals. The phototraps were uninstalled after five days of the exposure, when the accessible branches had been defoliated and the spots

Fig. 4.

Exemplary representation of a particular cattle grouping (on July 9, around 3 PM) with the standard deviational ellipse

Fig. 5.

Cattle browsing of the pollarded crown

Left: freshly pollarded young oak (July 7, after 12 PM); Right: the same pollarded crown almost 24 hours later, with six cows/heifers; the yellow line refers to the 2-m-wide buffer of the crown's projections used in the LTIa calculation

were no longer visited by cattle (Fig. 5). The phototraps collected 348 digital photographs and 607 short movie clips. We extracted the date and time of the animals' appearance, maximal number of animals consuming the arboreal forages, and the stack/crown abandonment time from the visual data. Thereafter, the stack/crown-specific timelines of livestock temporal impact on arboreal forages (LTIa) were calculated as:

$$LTIa = n_i \cdot t_i \cdot A_i^{-1}$$

where:

n_i – number of animals at the i -th stack/pollarded crown,

t_i – the i -th grouping duration,

A_i – the area of the 2-m-wide buffer of a stack/pollarded crown projection on the ground.

Nutritional characteristics of the wood-pasture fodder. To compare the nutritional potentials of tree leafage to that of the grassland herbaceous forage, we analysed leaves and twigs of six tree species, *i.e.* common oak, sycamore maple, hornbeam, silver birch, wild cherry, and alder (Fig. 3; *Fagus sylvatica* L. trees were not analysed because they are relatively old and tall), and two collective samples of above-ground parts (leaves, flowers, and stems) of herbaceous plants sickled at 1 cm aboveground on July 1st in two fenced-off parts of the pasture's open ryegrass-crested dogtail *Lolium-Cynosuretum* R.TX. 1937 grassland. Crude protein, crude fat, crude fibre, ash, and nitrogen-free extracts (NFE) were determined by AOAC methods (AOAC, 2020). Following a documented procedure (Zagała *et al.*, 2017), we determined the content of Ca, K, Mg, P, S, Mn, Zn, Fe, and Sr.

Results

VEGETATION STRUCTURE OF THE WOOD-PASTURE. In total, 137 herbaceous and semi-shrub species were identified in the wood-pasture's habitats, with 114 species affiliated in 15 phytosociological classes (23 spp. had no specific affiliation), corresponding with four vegetation types: grassland (61 spp.), ruderal vegetation (24 spp.), forests (20 spp.), and fringe shrubland (5 spp.). Regarding particular habitats, the richest was open grassland OGR, with 92 species, followed by semi-open wood SOW (57 spp.), pioneering groves PIG (56 spp.), riparian wood RIW (44 spp.), and close-canopy wood CCW (41 spp.).

The wood-pasture was dominated by OGR (49% of the area; Fig. 3), mainly constituted by perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L., on average of 14% cover contribution), bentgrass (*Agrostis capillaris* L., 11%), white clover (*Trifolium repens* L., 11%), blue grass (*Poa pratensis* L. s. str., 6%), red fescue (*Festuca rubra* L. s. STR., 5%), dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale* F. H. Wigg., 5%), creeping buttercup (*Ranunculus repens* L., 4%), moneywort (*Lysimachia nummularia* L., 4%), heal-all (*Prunella vulgaris* L., 3%) among other species. As many as 42 species in OGR (45% of OGR spp.) had a phytosociological affiliation in grassland: *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* R.Tx. 1937 (37 species), *Nardo-Callunetea* Prsg 1949 (4 sp.), and *Phragmitetea* R.Tx. et Prsg 1942 (1 sp.) (Fig. 6). The herbaceous layer of SOW (19% of the wood-pasture), had a very similar structure to OGR (Fig. 3, 6). Its major physiognomic difference was the presence of scattered trees as well as spiny and thorny shrubs, in particular, blackberries *Rubus* L. sp., dog rose *Rosa canina* L., and hawthorn *Crataegus* L. sp. Although the overall richness of herbaceous species was substantially lower, species groups' structure and actual species composition were similar to those of OGR. Bentgrass (11%), rough blue grass (*Poa trivialis* L., 10%), perennial ryegrass (9%), moneywort (9%), dandelion (6%), blue grass (6%), creeping buttercup (5%) dominated the SOW, and 33 out of all 57 SOW herbaceous species had a phytosociological affiliation in grassland classes: *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* (29 spp.), *Nardo-Callunetea* (3 spp.), and *Koelerio glaucae-Corynephoretea canescentis* Klika in Klika et Novak 1941 (1 sp.). Equally high participation of grasslands-affiliated species (57% – *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* 29 spp. and *Nardo-Callunetea* 3 spp.) occurred in PIG, covering 13% of the wood-pasture (Fig. 3, 6). The most abundant species in PIG was bentgrass (22%) and among the next nine most abundant taxa, seven were mentioned above as OGR and SOW co-dominating species, accompanied here by yarrow (*Achillea millefolium* L. s. STR., 6%) and ribwort plantain (*Plantago lanceolata* L., 3%). The RIW habitats, occupying 12% of the wood-pasture, revealed substantial differences to the former categories (Fig. 3, 6). Although its most abundant species was rough blue grass, contributing to 28% of the overall species abundance, the next most abundant species were associated with nitrogen-rich and moist sites. Some of these species include mannagrass (*Glyceria fluitans* (L.)

Fig. 6.

Vegetational composition of five habitat categories in the wood-pasture

Woodland, Grassland, Ruderal, Shrubland species belonging to forest (coniferous and deciduous), grassland, ruderal, and shrubland phytosociological classes, respectively; the vegetation habitat structure differs significantly between the habitats even when the most outlier CCW was not considered (Pearson's Chi-squared test, $\chi^2=37.703$, $df=9$, p -value <0.0001); for habitat categories see Figure 2.

R. Br., 8%), wood clubrush (*Scirpus sylvaticus* L., 7%), creeping buttercup (6%), ground elder (*Aegopodium podagraria* L., 6%), wood avens (*Geum urbanum* L., 5%), and herb-Robert (*Geranium robertianum* L., 5%). In CCW, occupying 6% of the wood-pasture, 12 forest species (*Querceto-Fageteta* Br.-Bl. et Vlieg. 1937 – 10 spp., *Quercetea robori-petraeae* Br.-Bl. et R.Tx. 1943 1 sp., *Epilobietea angustifolii* R.Tx. et Prsg 1950 1 sp.), including sanicle (*Sanicula europaea* L., 18%), wood anemone (*Anemone nemorosa* L., 14%), broad-leaved enchanter's nightshade (*Circaea lutetiana* L., 7%), and wild strawberry (*Fragaria vesca* L., 6%), were outnumbered by non-forest species, including 9 affiliated in open-grassland (such as common self-heal *Prunella vulgaris*, 6%, and moneywort, 5%) as well as 7 in ruderal vegetation (such as wood avens (7%) and herb-Robert (6%)) (Fig. 3, 6).

The multiple proportion test revealed significant differences of proportions of woodland to non-woodland herbaceous species among all five habitat categories ($\chi^2=154.97$, $df=4$, p -value<0.0001) as well as among particular pairs of habitats. In the latter case, the CCW was the most distinct category, significantly different from any other habitat. The most conspicuous difference occurred between CCW and OGR (2-sample test for equality of proportions with continuity correction $\chi^2=128.9$, $df=1$, p -value<0.0001). Considering the species affiliated in woodland plant communities as 'native' to CCW (while the non-woodland ones as 'alien') and the species affiliated in non-woodland communities as 'native' to OGR (while the woodland ones as 'alien'), the alien-to-native ratio was 0.60 in CCW and only 0.05 in OGR (Table 1).

SPATIOTEMPORAL USE OF THE WOOD-PASTURE BY CATTLE.

Habitats' preferences of the tracked cows and temporary cattle groupings. In order to investigate preferences of the tracked cows and cattle groupings, we have compared the time spent in each habitat with the share of a habitat's surface. If there were no preferences then the cows would graze along random routes over pasture. In such cases the distribution of time spent should be similar to the distribution of the surface of habitats under study. Since the share of the surface is not random, we used a single proportion test. The four tagged-cows' visits in RIW and CCW were less than their shares (RIW: $p=0.057$; CCW: $p=0.009$) in the wood-pasture, while no significant differences were observed for OGR ($p=0.694$), Pion PIG ($p=0.106$) and SOW ($p=0.133$) (Fig. 7). The order of the cows' visits was consistent with the order of the share of the five habitats (OGR>SOW>PIG>RIW>CCW) in the wood-pasture (Fig. 7).

As many as 44 temporary cattle groupings (TCGs), totalling 1119 animals, were mapped: 12 on July 7, 16 on July 8, and 16 on July 9 (Fig. 4, 8). Particular TCGs consisted of 8 to 51 animals, extending from 280 m² to 13800 m², and lasting from 5 to 130 minutes. Overall, there were significant differences between neither the daily number of animals in the TCGs nor the daily areas of their SD-ellipses (Fig. 8). The relative frequency of the use of CCW, RIW and SOW habitats by TCGs were significantly lower than their shares (CCW: $p=0.054$, RIW: $p=0.017$ and SOW: $p=0.062$), while there were no significant differences for OGR ($p=0.670$) and PIG ($p=0.197$) (Fig. 8). However, the order of habitats' uses by the TCGs differed (OGR>PIG>SOW>CCW>RIW) from that of the habitats' spatial shares (OGR>SOW>PIG>RIW>CCW).

Table 1.

Total number of herbaceous species recorded in all relevés representing particular habitat categories, broken down by species affiliation in woodland and non-woodland plant communities

Species affiliation	CCW	OGR	PIG	RIW	SOW
Woodland communities	48	13	14	16	9
Grassland and ruderal communities	29	249	93	65	99

Fig. 7.

Comparison of the average proportions of the habitats use by the cattle to the shares [%] of these habitats in the whole wood-pasture area; the numbers above the first and second bars are the p-values of the single proportion test

For habitat categories see Figure 2.

Fig. 8.

Comparison of the temporary groupings' parameters in three consecutive days

The tiny squares in boxes represent medians; lower and upper edges of each box represent Q1 and Q3 (the first and the third quartile) respectively; the box whiskers refer to the min and max values in each set respectively; p represents the p -value of Kruskal-Wallis test; N means number; and SD ellipses means standard deviational ellipses)

Livestock temporal impact on herbaceous and arboreal forages. The total livestock temporal impact on herbaceous forages (LTI) ranged from close to 0 to 4.8 individual-hours per 100 m⁻², and there was no significant difference between the daily LTI values (Fig. 9). The dynamics of foraging on the branches' stacks and the whole crowns (LTIa) were similar (Arb1 vs. Arb2; Fig. 9). Most of the cattle's foraging-related presence around the two forms of arboreal forages occurred during the daytime, with two distinguishable peaks – one between 5 and 8 AM and the other one between 10 AM and 2 PM. Generally, either the first or the second visit had the highest LTIa value, which decreased with subsequent visits due to the fodder depletion. Overall, the LTIa was substantially higher than the LTI recorded during the three days of observation (Fig. 9).

Comparison of nutritional composition of herbaceous and arboreal forages. Tree leaves were significantly richer in proteins, fat, and nitrogen-free extracts (NFE) than the herbaceous forages (Table 2; fourth column). Tree twigs had a higher content of fibre than both tree leaves and herbaceous

Fig. 9.

Livestock temporal impact (medians, Q1-Q3, min-max) on herb layer during three consecutive days (Jul 7-9) in observed cattle natural groupings (LTI) vs. the impact on experimentally provided stacks of the arboreal forage (LTIa)

Arb1 – stacks of branches, Arb2 – felled whole crowns; table in the top: p-values of the multiple comparisons on ranks of five independent samples; Kruskal-Wallis test: H (4, N=69)=24.024, p=0.0001

Table 2.

Comparison of nutritional composition of herbaceous forages (including leaves, flowers, and aboveground stems regarded as 'Herbs'), tree leaves (Leaves), and tree twigs (Twigs)

Nutrient	K-W p		Leaves	Twigs	Herbs	M _{min}	M _{max}
Protein	0.000	herbs	0.021↑	0.023↓		<i>Bp.t</i>	<i>Ag.l</i>
		leaves		0.000↓	10.732	5.117	19.860
Fat	0.000	herbs	0.001↑	1.000		<i>Ap.t</i>	<i>Ag.l</i>
		leaves		0.000↓	2.204	0.722	6.657
Fibre	0.000	herbs	0.002↓	0.210↑		<i>Ca.l</i>	<i>Cb.t</i>
		leaves		0.000↑	33.886	16.700	45.334
Ash	0.000	herbs	0.092↓	0.000↓		<i>Bp.t</i>	
		leaves		0.000↓	9.523	2.691	9.523
NFE	0.000	herbs	0.000↑	0.002↑			<i>Cb.l</i>
		leaves		0.049↓	43.784	43.784	55.512

Note: NFE – nitrogen-free extracts; K-W p – Kruskal-Wallis test's p-values; values in 'Leaves' and 'Twigs' columns indicate p-values of the multiple comparisons on ranks with 'Herbs', and 'Leaves' samples (third column); ↑ and ↓ respectively indicate superiority and inferiority of an element content median in 'Leaves' and 'Twigs' compared to 'Herbs' and 'Leaves'; values in the 'Herbs' column indicate median of an element content; M_{min} and M_{max} respectively denote maximum and minimum median values attributable to 'Herbs' (blank) or leaves (.l) or twigs (.t) of particular tree species. Ag – *Alnus glutinosa*, Ap – *Acer pseudoplatanus*, Bp – *Betula pendula*, Ca – *Cerasus avium*, Cb – *Carpinus betulus*, Qr – *Quercus robur*

forages (Table 2; fifth column). The herbaceous forages, however, had a substantially higher content of ash than the arboreal forages. Except for ash, the highest medians of the contents of nutritional components were found in the leaves of alder (proteins, fat) and hornbeam (NFE), and in hornbeam twigs (fibre; Table 2).

Both the tree leaves and twigs had higher calcium and strontium contents than the herbaceous forages (Table 3). The differences between the contents of other elements in the tree leaves

Table 3.

Comparison of herbaceous forage (including leaves, flowers, and aboveground stems referred as 'Herbs'), tree leaves (Leaves), and tree twigs (Twigs) with regards to the content of selected elements ($\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ of dry mass)

Nutrient	K-W p		Leaves	Twigs	Herbs	M_{\min}	M_{\max}
Ca	0.000	herbs	0.000↑	0.000↑			<i>Ca.l</i>
		leaves		0.996↓	5.482	5.482	16.630
K	0.000	herbs	0.139↓	0.000↓		<i>Bp.t</i>	<i>Ca.l</i>
		leaves		0.000↓	16.962	8.696	17.164
Mg	0.000	herbs	0.409↑	0.001↓		<i>Ag.t</i>	<i>Ca.l</i>
		leaves		0.000↓	2.128	0.606	4.063
P	0.000	herbs	1.000	0.000↓		<i>Ca.t</i>	
		leaves		0.000↓	2.247	0.896	2.247
S	0.000	herbs	1.000	0.000↓		<i>Ca.t</i>	<i>Ag.l</i>
		leaves		0.000↓	1.634	0.430	1.753
Mn	0.008	herbs	0.144↑	1.000		<i>Ca.t</i>	<i>Cb.l</i>
		leaves		0.010↓	0.321	0.116	1.987
Fe	0.066	herbs	0.066↓	0.133↓		<i>Ap.t</i>	
		leaves		1.000	0.175	0.050	0.175
Al	0.000	herbs	0.194↓	0.000↓		<i>Qr.t</i>	<i>Cb.l</i>
		leaves		0.003↓	0.177	0.023	0.443
Sr	0.000	herbs	0.008↑	0.000↑			<i>Cb.l</i>
		leaves		0.005↑	0.020	0.020	0.043
Zn	0.020	herbs	1.000	0.052↑		<i>Ca.l</i>	<i>Bp.l</i>
		leaves		0.082↑	0.024	0.013	0.122

See footnote of Table 2 for the explanation

and herbaceous forages were either negligible or insignificant, except for smaller content of iron in tree leaves. Overall, twigs had smaller content of the elements than the herbaceous or tree leaves tissues. Of all the ten elements, only P and Fe were higher in the herbal tissue than in the leaf tissue of trees (Table 3).

Discussion

The Subcarpathian region, SE Poland, is the second most forested region of the country (forest cover contributes to 40% of the land base). One fourth of its contemporary woodlands emerged after WWII, due to the massive depopulation of the countryside and land abandonment (Zarzycki *et al.*, 2022) Although there are relatively large fragments of natural old-growth forests in Eastern Carpathians (*e.g.* Jaworski *et al.*, 2002; Spracklen and Spracklen, 2020), numerous pockets of old trees in the foothill zone have developed from the semi-open grove enclaves or wider woodland-grassland ecotones in traditional agricultural landscapes (Öllerer, 2014; Bobiec *et al.*, 2019). Their abandonment, in particular, cessation of livestock grazing of wooded margins, has led to a radical change in the ecological characteristics of the woodland-farmland interface, transformed from the semi-open ecotone to the narrow, sharp ecological barriers, sealing off woods from neighbouring open habitats (Wolański *et al.*, 2021).

Our study demonstrates various aspects of livestock grazing in a treed landscape mosaic, which has almost entirely vanished in the Central Europe's countryside due to the farmland abandonment, intensification of animal production, forestry specialisation, and the legal ban on forest grazing. We assessed the vegetation structure and silvopastoral potential of a wood-pasture,

which developed during twelve years of free-range grazing of a feral post-agricultural landscape that was abandoned ten years earlier. Most of such post-agricultural lands in the proximity of Rzeszów city either continue succession towards woodland or, being commodified, undergo peri-urban, mostly residential, development (Bobieć *et al.*, 2021).

The vegetation inventory proved that twelve years of cattle grazing has turned an apparently amorphic abandoned farmland ('a shrubby mess' – D. Jaworski, personal communication) into a well-established mosaic of diverse patches of five distinguished types of vegetation: treeless grassland, pioneering groves, riparian woods, semi-open woods, and close-canopy woods. While the birch- and aspen-dominated groves emerged on the plough field fallows, semi-open wood, with a higher tree species and, apparently, age diversity, imply a different tree recruitment mechanism. This likely involved a gradual and slow process of grassland colonisation by heavy-seeded, zoochorically dispersed tree species, such as oak, hornbeam, sycamore, and wild cherry (*cf.* Bobieć *et al.*, 2018). Despite the limited acreage of the close-canopy wood habitat, the presence of ancient woodland, poorly dispersible 'ancient forest' species, *e.g.*, *Anemone nemorosa* and *Oxalis acetosella* L. in the herbaceous layer (Peterken and Game, 1984; Dzwonko and Gawroński, 1994) indicate that visiting cattle is not detrimental to the woodland aspect of those habitats. Quite the opposite, their relatively poor ground layer, despite the tree canopy's heavy shade, has been substantially enriched by shade-intolerant grassland and ruderal species, most likely spread by livestock. As the present close canopy woods' position corresponds with the forest area depicted on the Austro-Hungarian military map of the mid-1800s (Arcanum-maps, 2022), it may imply that the present cattle visits in the woods resembles what was common in the foothills' silvopastoral landscape of 150 years ago (*cf.* Bobieć *et al.*, 2019). Although the share of wooded communities (in particular, dominated by birch, aspen, and alder) substantially increased in the local landscape during the first two decades following the abandonment, the introduction of grazing in 2008 prevented further succession of woody species and stabilised the landscape's mosaic structure. In general, the structure of the cattle's use of habitats did not differ from the expected pattern derived from the overall landscape's mosaic composition. Among the few exceptions, pioneering birch woods were more often (than expected) visited by larger groups of cattle, while semi-open and riparian woods were less visited. The attractiveness of the pioneering stands might be related to their ambient semi-shadow microclimate, providing shelter from summer heat, and, simultaneously, securing better growing conditions for the herb layer than close-canopy woods. The lesser use of the riparian habitat might be explained by its difficult topography, involving steep scarps and soft boggy bottom. In general, the cattle revealed the grazing preference towards grassland, whether open or scarcely treed, limiting their presence in close-canopy woods to livestock passages and to actionless stays of small, seeking shelter, groups.

Although the study did not specifically address the effect of browsing on tree regeneration, in the south-eastern part of the wood-pasture, we observed a 'brush' of the middle-aged hornbeam saplings, evenly 'coppiced' by cattle, just in the way the wild ungulates browse this species in the Białowieża Forest (*cf.* Bobieć *et al.*, 2011; Kowalczyk *et al.*, 2021). In general, except for the locally occurring sprouts and saplings, and a small grove of the young alder-birch thicket in the south eastern part of the wood-pasture, the livestock had almost no unaided access to the arboreal forage. Our experimental feeding revealed a conspicuous appeal of such a diet to Galloway cattle. However, except for sycamore maple's leafage being apparently preferred to the neighbouring stack of black alder's one, we did not detect any selection preferences amongst the assessed trees. Overall, the intensity of consumption of the experimentally provided arboreal forage by

the cattle was 4.5 folds higher than that of the herbaceous one. Thus, our experiment revealed high overall attractiveness of the arboreal fodder supplement to the regular herbaceous diet of cattle. We are, however, aware that a new, well-designed study would be needed for ranking the cattle's preference for the arboreal forage of different tree species.

There is plenty evidence indicating beneficial effects of the arboreal forages on both livestock health and environment. However, despite the well documented history of silvopastoralism (Vandermeulen *et al.*, 2018), the arboreal forage use in Europe has been marginalised due to the intensification of animal production and strict grazing separation from wooded areas (Slotte, 2001; Bobiec *et al.*, 2019). Perhaps the most important immediate effect of solitary trees and scattered canopy of treed grassland is the shade shelter, benefiting both herbaceous vegetation and animals, contributing to their better physiological performance (Treydte *et al.*, 2007; van Laer *et al.*, 2015). During prolonged droughts, the role of arboreal forages may shift from diet supplement to a more basic source of fresh forage (Moore *et al.*, 2003; Papanastis *et al.*, 2008).

The tree hay of silvopastoral woods may compensate for the herbaceous forage scarcity resulting either from the natural soil's poverty, its degradation, desiccation, or overgrazing. Our analyses show that the tree leaves are richer in Ca, Sr, Mn, protein, fat, and NFE (*i.e.*, primarily sugars) than the herbaceous forage. Although the tree twigs are poorer (compared to herbaceous vegetation) in most of the analysed elements (except for Sr, Ca, and Zn), they contain higher quantities of NFE and fibre. This partially corroborates with the data reported from tropical and subtropical regions, emphasising the tree foliage to be a rich source of Ca, protein, and fat (Gowda, 2004; Bakshi and Wadhwa, 2012; Tefera and Mlambo, 2017). In addition, the arboreal forages are important sources of compounds responsible for the ruminant's health and self-medication. For instance, abundant in twigs fibre is necessary for the performance of the herbivore's digestive-intestinal system (Mateos *et al.*, 2019) and condensed tannins (abundant in both *Alnus glutinosa* and *Quercus robur* tissues (González-Hernández *et al.*, 2003) protect animals against parasites (Provenza *et al.*, 2003; Lisonbee *et al.*, 2009), reduce nitrogen volatility (Grainger *et al.*, 2009) and methane emission (Grainger *et al.*, 2009 and therein referred authors). The microelement strontium, relatively abundant in the analysed plant tissues (especially in hornbeam leaves), promotes the uptake of calcium, which strengthens animals' bones and minimises the risk of osteoporosis (Marie *et al.*, 2001; Nielsen, 2004). The beneficial effect of oak leafage on the livestock's health has been confirmed by the Borówki's cattle keeper. According to his account, after the long stay in the shed during the cold and wet 2023 spring, the animals suffered from severe diarrhoea, of which the pharmaceutical treatment would be very expensive. Thus, as a first-aid measure, the leafy branches shredded from the wood-pasture's oaks were provided to the livestock. As we were informed, the self-medication proved to be 100% efficient, bringing all ill cattle to swift recovery (S. Pełkala – personal communication).

We are aware of the study's major limitations of our research, resulting primarily from the fact that the studied wood-pasture was the only such case of the landscape's transformation management in the sub-Carpathian region through free range cattle grazing. Thus, instead of a systematic, in-depth analysis, best recommended in studies of well-functioning systems, we applied a more rudimentary characterization of selected features of that, though young and secondary, unique wood pasture. Despite these limitations however, we believe that the study provides a valuable insight into the potential of cattle grazing as a successful driver of transformation from post-agricultural, overgrown abandoned land to working silvopastoral landscapes. In most of temperate Europe, such landscapes are a missing aspect of the woodland spectrum from artificial

schematic tree plantations to managed forests, to non-intervention protected areas. Scaling up the successful experience of the small village in the neighbourhood of Rzeszów to vast tracts of abandoned sub-Carpathian farmlands, while restoring their economic capacity, could contribute to higher woodlands' diversity, compromising neither the productivity of existing managed forests nor interrupting continuity of non-intervention approach in protected forest areas. In our view, letting Galloway cattle to graze and shape the piece of feral landscape was a crucial decision, determining the spectrum of immediate or potentially available ecosystem services (Fig. 10). Allowing further spontaneous successional development, encroachment and growth of woody vegetation, would homogenise the landscape structure, losing openness and the associated traits and functions. In temperate Europe, as in sub-Carpathian region specifically,, dense forest is not a scarce resource. As shown by maps of the Potential Natural Vegetation (*sensu* R. Tüxen – Tüxen, 1956), the dominating Europe's PNVs are forests (*e.g.* Matuszkiewicz, 2008a, b). Therefore, the abandonment of agricultural activity triggers the secondary succession, leading inevitably to establishment of close forests, and narrowing the spectrum of ecosystem services to the ones specifically dependent on dense woodlands (Fig. 10). Although such a process would fit the strongly lobbied postulate of land sparing to natural processes and afforestation (Navarro and Pereira, 2012; EC, 2021), we argue that it would not be a universally beneficial solution with respect to the optimal provision of the ecosystem values. We believe that a more diverse and dynamic landscape, such as working wood-pasture, in the present context, might be a far better response to environmental and human challenges of the future (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10.

Conceptual model of the alternative changes in land-use following agricultural abandonment, with respect to the structure of ecosystem services

Conclusions

- ✦ This study proved that grazing by a robust breed of cattle can transform partly-wooded post-agricultural land into a dynamic mosaic landscape, consisting of interconnected open grasslands and various facets of woodland, which are almost absent in contemporary forest landscapes. Due to their different dynamics, spatial patterns, and adaptation to environmental conditions, silvopastoral habitats should be appreciated as invaluable enrichment of simplified and homogenised vegetation, such as modern croplands, treeless grasslands, or dense forests. Increasing tracts of abandoned and growing feral farmlands could be transformed into the future integrated silvopastoral landscapes with a wide range of provision, regulatory, and social ecosystem services.
- ✦ We argue against the use of abandoned farmlands as a mere land base for any alternative projects, such as residential development, wind or photovoltaic farms, schematic tree planting, or leaving for natural succession. Abandoned farmlands, in particular, in suboptimal growing conditions of cultural landscapes shaped by traditional, small-holder farming – such as in the Carpathian foothills – inherit the rich legacy of landscape structures and its particular components (including open grown trees, semi-open woods, groves, and copses). Such habitats, patterns, and related processes can best be preserved if incorporated into a multipurpose, land-use model capitalising on that inherited diversity.
- ✦ Although we do not provide a universal solution for all particular cases, our results present strong premises indicating that transformation of abandoned farmlands into working wood-pastures would be a feasible response to multiple environmental, conservation, and socio-economic challenges, and to the increasing demand for various ecosystem services. The development of such working wooded landscapes would require a knowledge sharing and cooperation platform between land owners, farmers, foresters, and field ecologists. Such a cooperation is necessary to secure a trade-off between grazing intensity and the fodder (both herbaceous and arboreal) regenerative capacity. Besides the wood-pastures' 'target' animal and wood production, their cooperative management should provide a wide range of regulatory and social services, including carbon sequestration, high biodiversity, pollination, seed dispersal, weed control, and scenic beauty.
- ✦ The successful transformation of abandoned sub-Carpathian farmlands towards working silvopastoral landscapes would require a multidisciplinary research programme, necessary to define the criteria and assess the feasibility of such a transformation with regard to ecological and socio-economical aspects. The collected information might contribute to spatially explicit models of whole-regions' development, involving the sustainable use of their rural landscapes.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization – A.B., Ł.K.; methodology – A.B., Ł.K., P.W., R.T.-S., G.Z., and S.W.; software – S.W.; validation – A.B., Ł.K., P.W., R.T.-S., G.Z., and S.W.; formal analysis – A.B., Ł.K., P.W., R.T.-S., G.Z., T.O.M., and S.W.; investigation – A.B., A.D., Ł.K., P.W., R.T.-S., and G.Z.; resources – A.B., R.T.-S., and G.Z.; data curation – A.B., P.W., and S.W.; writing-original draft preparation – A.B., T.O.M., R.B.; writing-review and editing – A.B., T.O.M.; visualization – A.B., S.W.; supervision – A.B. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

The Authors declare no conflicts of interests.

Funding source

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant number 862993) in the framework of the Agroforestry and Mixed farming systems-Participatory research to drive the transition to a resilient and efficient land use in Europe (AGROMIX) project and by the College of Natural Sciences, University of Rzeszów.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their appreciation to Chmielnik-Zdrój S.A. and its staff for opening the wood-pasture for this research, their friendly support and invaluable pieces of advice.

Supplementary materials

Any source data will be provided at request.

Data availability statement

Any source data will be provided at request.

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Przywracanie wypasu bydła w opuszczonych gospodarstwach. Lekcja z sylwopastoralnej intensyfikacji ekologicznej w krajobrazie karpackiego pogórza południowo-wschodniej Polski

Rozwój w XVIII w. nowoczesnego, wyspecjalizowanego i ekonomicznie wydajnego modelu leśnictwa zasadniczo zmienił strukturalne cechy i dynamikę lasów europejskich. W szczególności zakaz wypasu zwierząt, niemal powszechnie wprowadzony w lasach Europy Środkowej, uruchomił proces rozwoju cienoznośnego podszytu, doprowadzając do zaniku półotwartych gajów i do funkcjonalnej ekologicznej izolacji lasów od ich szerszego krajobrazowego kontekstu. Niezależnie od tego znaczne połacie gruntów rolnych zostały w wyniku niedawnych społeczno-gospodarczych przeobrażeń porzucone, co prowadzi do przekształcenia silnie zróżnicowanej wsi w zdziczałe krajobrazy pokryte w coraz większym stopniu roślinnością drzewiastą. Choć zmiany te zgodne są z postulatem globalnej i europejskiej polityki przeciwdziałania zmianom klimatycznym, można przypuszczać, że „ekologiczna intensyfikacja” porzuconych krajobrazów może przynieść większe korzyści niż trwałe porzucenie użytkowania rolniczego. W celu weryfikacji powyższej intuicji objęto badaniami jednostkę krajobrazową na terenie wsi Borówki na Pogórzu Dynowskim w powiecie rzeszowskim. Obszar badawczy stanowiło ok. 16-hektarowe ogrodzone pastwisko, utworzone w 2008 r. na porzuconych ok. 10 lat wcześniej gruntach porolnych (ryc. 1). Pastwisko przedstawia nieregularną mozaikę 5 wyróżnionych biotopów: bezdrzewnej murawy (49% powierzchni), murawy z rzadkim „sawannowym” drzewostanem i kępami jeżyn (19%), pionierskiego drzewostanu z dominacją brzozy lub/i olszy (13%), zbiorowisk łągowych (12%) oraz zwartego lasu (6%) (ryc. 2 i 3). Na podstawie udziału 4 wyróżnionych grup gatunków (łąkowo-pastwiskowych, ruderalnych, roślinności okrajków, leśnych) wskazano na potencjalną rolę bydła w wymianie gatunków roślin między sąsiadującymi biotopami (tab. 1; ryc. 6). Biotopem, w którym najliczniej i najczęściej przebywało bydło, były bezdrzewne murawy, a stosunkowo najrzadziej odwiedzonym – zwarty las (ryc. 2, 3 i 7). Zajmowany obszar i licznosc tworzonych przez zwierzęta zgrupowań utrzymywały się na zbliżonym poziomie w ciągu 3 dni rejestracji zgrupowań (ryc. 8). Przeprowadzony eksperyment, polegający na dostarczeniu zwierzętom zazwyczaj niedostępnego (z powodu wysokości drzew) pokarmu pędowo-liściowego, pozyskanego z występujących lokalnie drzew, wykazał jego bardzo wysoką atrakcyjność, również względem pokarmu zielonego (ryc. 4 i 9). Porównanie pokarmu zielono-trawiastego z pokarmem pędowo-liściowym pozyskanym z obecnych na pastwisku drzew wykazało, że ze względu na skład chemiczny oraz wartości odżywcze liściarka może być bardzo cennym uzupełnieniem konwencjonalnej diety pastwiskowej roślinożerców (tab. 2 i 3). Przeprowadzone badania potwierdziły przypuszczenie, że wypas – nie stanowiąc zagrożenia dla środowiska zwartego lasu – może odgrywać decydującą rolę jako skuteczny czynnik powstrzymujący postęp sukcesji ekologicznej oraz stabilizujący mozaikową strukturę częściowo zadrzewionego krajobrazu, którego ważnym elementem są m.in. półotwarte zadrzewienia – gaje uwarunkowane presją wypasu zwierząt. Porównanie potencjalnego znaczenia świadczeń ekosystemowych dla alternatywnych scenariuszy rozwoju jednostki krajobrazowej (spontaniczna nieograniczona sukcesja ekologiczna vs. presja wypasu) wskazuje na zdecydowanie większe korzyści z realizacji wypasu (ryc. 10). Choć nie jest to propozycja uniwersalnego rozwiązania, możliwego do zastosowania we wszystkich przypadkach, przedstawione wyniki

dostarczają mocnych przesłanek na rzecz transformacji opuszczonych rolniczych jednostek krajobrazowych w czynne zadrzewione pastwiska, jako właściwej odpowiedzi na liczne wyzwania środowiskowe, ekologiczne i społeczno-ekonomiczne oraz na rosnące zapotrzebowanie na różnorodne świadczenia ekosystemowe. Pomyślna transformacja opuszczonych obszarów wiejskich wymagać będzie zdefiniowania kryteriów i wskaźników zmian, a przede wszystkim odpowiedniego studium wykonalności w odniesieniu do poszczególnych regionów.